

1 **Contrasting net primary productivity and carbon sink strength between**
2 **neighboring stands of *Quercus robur* (L.) and *Pinus sylvestris* (L.)**

3

4

5

6 **J. Curiel Yuste**, B. Konôpka, I.A. Janssens, K. Coenen, C. W. Xiao and R. Ceulemans

7

8 University of Antwerp (UA), Department of Biology, Research Group of Plant and
9 Vegetation Ecology, Universiteitsplein 1, B-2610 Wilrijk, Belgium.

10

11

12

13

14 Address of correspondence: Jorge Curiel Yuste

15 Dept. Biology, University of Antwerp, UA

16 Universiteitsplein 1

17 B-2610, Wilrijk, Belgium

18 Fax: xx32/3/820.22.71

19 e-mail: jorge.curielyuste@ua.ac.be

20

21

22

23

1 **Abstract**

2

3 Standing biomass, net primary production (NPP) and soil carbon (C) pools were studied
4 in a 67-year-old pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur* L.) stand and a neighboring 74-year-old
5 Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) stand in the Belgian Campine region. Despite a 14%
6 lower tree density and a lower tree height in the oak stand, standing biomass was slightly
7 higher than in the pine stand (177 t ha⁻¹ and 169 t ha⁻¹ in oaks and pines, respectively),
8 indicating that individual trees of similar diameter contained more biomass. Moreover, NPP
9 in the oaks was more than double that in the pine stand (17.7 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and 8.1 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹,
10 respectively). On the contrary, soil C pools were much larger in the pine than in the oak
11 stand (150.8 t C ha⁻¹ and 92.2 t C ha⁻¹, respectively) and soil C sequestration (estimated
12 both from soil C measurements as from the difference between litter inputs and
13 heterotrophic respiration) in the pines appeared extremely high. We hypothesize that the
14 ongoing acidification in the pine stand reduced both soil nutrient availability and
15 heterotrophic activity. This, combined with the already recalcitrance to decay of pine
16 litter resulted in the observed accumulation of organic matter. The subsequent
17 immobilization of nutrients in the organic matter, combined with the already nutrient-
18 poor soil conditions, resulted in a decrease in total NPP in time as well as in a substantial
19 shift in the allocation of NPP toward fine roots. In the oak stand, litter is less recalcitrant
20 to decay and soil acidity is less severe. Hence, organic matter does not accumulate and
21 nutrients are recycled. This probably explains why NPP in the oaks is much higher than
22 in the pines and why only a small proportion of NPP is allocated to fine roots.

23

24

25 Key words: allometric relationships, biomass distribution, NPP, nutrient stress,
26 pedunculate oak, Scots pine, soil carbon,

27

1 **Introduction**

2

3 Analyses based on observed atmospheric CO₂ concentrations and ¹³CO₂ suggest a strong
4 Northern Hemisphere terrestrial sink (Ciais et al. 1995), which is largely due to forest re-
5 growth and thus to immobilization in woody biomass and soil organic matter (IPCC,
6 2001). Net primary production (NPP), the net immobilization of atmospheric CO₂ in
7 plant biomass, is thus a key C-flux in the global carbon cycle and hence highly relevant
8 to the assessment of impacts of-and feedbacks to climatic change (Cramer et al. 2003).
9 Nonetheless, complete ecosystem-scale NPP estimates are rare, mainly because of the
10 difficulty in estimating belowground NPP (Reich and Bolstad 2001). Therefore, more
11 ground-based observations of carbon pools and carbon pool changes in forest ecosystems
12 are needed to improve our understanding of the global carbon cycle. Temperate forests
13 constitute one of the dominant forest types on the earth (Reich and Bolstad 2001). Factors
14 indicated to control aboveground NPP (ANPP) in temperate ecosystems are temperature
15 and moisture (Gholz 1982, Running 1994), nitrogen availability (Reich et al. 1997) and
16 mean annual temperature of the region where the planted trees originate from (Oleksyn et
17 al. 2000). There appear to be no overall differences in ANPP between coniferous and
18 deciduous temperate forests (Schulze 1982, Reich and Bolstad 2001). The growth
19 patterns of these two different plant functional types are adjusted to very different
20 environmental conditions, and depending on the habitat one strategy is likely to be more
21 successful than the other one. For instance, conifers are generally more efficient in harsh
22 environments, where nutrients are recycled slowly, because they economize on the
23 amount of C and nutrients allocated to new foliage. In contrast, deciduous trees are
24 generally more efficient in milder climates, because they require faster nutrient cycling to
25 construct large amounts of new foliage each year (Schulze 1982).

26 In this study we report complete NPP estimates for 2 different species growing within the
27 same forest (de Inslag; de Pury 1999, Janssens et al. 2000). ‘De Inslag’ is a very patchy
28 forest growing under NW-European temperate maritime conditions and a very good site
29 to test for differences between contrasting vegetation types: Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*
30 L.), an evergreen conifer and pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur* L.), a broadleaf deciduous
31 tree species. Pedunculate oak, one of the most representative species of the temperate

1 forest, occupies the whole of the Atlantic region (high rainfall) and the western transition
2 zone of the central continental regions (cold winters, moderately warm summers)
3 (Dobris Assessment 1995). In the Belgian Campine region, pedunculate oak is by far the
4 most distributed deciduous tree species. Scots pine is naturally distributed from Scotland
5 to eastern Siberia and between the boreal and temperate vegetation zones as far south as
6 Spain, where occupies mountains up to 2000 m elevation (Stenberg et al. 1994).
7 The main aim of this study was to estimate the standing biomass, NPP and C pools in a
8 stand dominated by pedunculate oaks and a stand dominated by Scots pine growing
9 within the same forest. Because both vegetation types differ largely in their annual soil C
10 emissions (twice as high in the oak plot; Curiel Yuste et al. 2004) and soil C fluxes are
11 related to forest productivity (Janssens et al. 2001), we hypothesize that also NPP will be
12 much higher in the oak plot than in the pine plot.
13

1 **Materials and methods**

2

3 *Plot description*

4 The experimental forest 'De Inslag' is located in Brasschaat, 20 km NE of Antwerp in the
5 Belgian Campine region (51°18' N and 4° 31' E). 'De Inslag' is a level-II observation
6 plot of the European Programme for Intensive Monitoring of Forest Ecosystems (EC
7 regulation No. 3528/86 and UN/ECE), and is managed by the Institute for Forestry and
8 Game Management (Flanders, Belgium). This 'urban' mixed forest (150 ha) is dominated
9 by two species, *i.e.* Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*, L.) which covers 50% of the surface area
10 and pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*, L) which covers 35 % of the surface area. The
11 Scots pines were planted in 1929, and the pedunculate oaks were planted in 1936.

12 The site has a temperate maritime climate, with long-term mean annual temperature of 9.8
13 °C, and, respectively, 3° C and 18° C as long-term mean temperatures of the coldest and
14 warmest month (Janssens et al., 1999). Mean annual precipitation is 750 mm. Site
15 topography is almost flat (slope: 0.3%), and the elevation is 16 m. The forest has a
16 moderately wet, sandy soil with a distinct humus and/or iron B-horizon (Baeyens et al.,
17 1993). The soil type is a psammentic haplumbrept (U.S.D.A. classification) or an umbric
18 regosol (F.A.O. classification). The site has poor drainage due to a clay layer at a depth of
19 1.5 to 2 m. The soil is moist, but rarely saturated, due to the high hydraulic conductivity
20 in the upper layers (sand). Soil water content (SWC) typically fluctuates around field
21 capacity (0.123 m³ m⁻³). More detailed information on the soil and local climatic conditions
22 can be found in Baeyens et al. (1993), Janssens et al. (1999) and Kowalski et al. (2000).

23 This study is based on the results obtained in two neighbouring stands, dominated
24 respectively by Scots pine and pedunculate oak. The Scots pine stand covers a surface of
25 aprox. 1.7 ha and the understorey is dominated mainly by mosses, grasses such as
26 *Molinia caerulea* (L.) and Scots pine seedlings. The pedunculate oak stand covers a
27 surface of aprox. 1.9 ha and the understorey is dominated also by mosses, and grasses.

28

29 *Forest inventory*

30 Detailed forest inventories were made in the pine stand in winter 2000-2001, winter 2001-
31 2002 and winter 2003-2004. Forest inventories in the pedunculate oak stand were carried

1 out in winter 2000-2001 and winter 2003-2004 as well, thus, with three growing seasons in
2 between both inventories. Measurements included DBH and tree height. In total 571 trees
3 were measured in the oaks and 619 trees in the pine. The rest of the tree population is
4 composed by other broadleaf species, some autochthonous such as *Betula pendula* or *Sorbus*
5 *aucuparia*, and some introduced such as *Quercus rubra* or *Castanea sativa*.

6 7 *Estimation of biomass*

8 Total biomass was defined as the sum of dry mass of stems, branches, needles, cones, coarse
9 roots and fine roots of all trees in each stand. Destructive measurements were performed
10 during two different field campaigns. The methodology followed at each location differed
11 slightly as described below.

12
13 Pines. In February 2002, nine sample trees of different stem diameter and representative of
14 the mean of their diameter classes were selected for harvest and destructive measurements to
15 estimate stand biomass. For more information on the destructive harvest and allometric
16 relationship establishment see Xiao et al. (2003). Allometric relationships were established
17 between stem, branch and needle biomass (both age classes), and several tree characteristics.
18 Because the allometric relationships with DBH only were consistently good (adjusted R^2
19 highest or very close), and because DBH is easy to measure, we decided to use the biomass –
20 DBH relationships to estimate biomass at the stand level (Figure 1 and Table 1). Stem, branch
21 and needle biomass was thus scaled-up to the stand level by combining these allometric
22 relationships with the DBH inventory of the entire stand.

23 Cone biomass was not measured. However, Helmisaari et al. (2002) reported that cone
24 biomass in Scots pine was very similar to cone NPP. Therefore cone biomass was assumed
25 equal to cone litterfall data.

26 For coarse root (> 5 mm) biomass, the allometric equation established in Janssens et al. (1999)
27 using data of four trees excavated in 1997 was slightly changed. Because in that study coarse
28 root biomass was not measured on the tallest trees, scaling with this allometric relationship
29 will be uncertain for the taller trees (Xiao et al. 2003). Therefore, in 2002 an entire root system
30 of a large tree (DBH = 41.7 cm) was excavated, oven-dried (15 days, 70 °C) and weighed.

1 Using the five root systems a new allometric equation between DBH and coarse root biomass
2 was then established (Table 1).

3 Both biomass and necromass of fine and small roots were repeatedly estimated in 2003
4 by core sampling. Samples were collected in the first weeks of February, April, June,
5 August and October 2003. At each sampling date, 25 soil columns of almost 40 cm long
6 were taken with a metal auger with an inner diameter of 7.0 cm. Then, the soil columns
7 were separated into the organic horizon (O) including the dark uppermost layer of the
8 mineral soil (A₁, 1 to 2.5 cm thick), and subsequent 10-cm thick soil layers, i.e. pure
9 mineral soil with depths 0-10, 10-20, 20-30 cm. Roots were manually picked out of the
10 samples, washed and sorted into three diameter classes: 0-1, 1-2, and 2-5 mm. Live and
11 dead roots were separated by visual inspection. Roots considered as live had lighter
12 colour than dead ones, typical with high resilience, firm and good cohesion between the
13 cortex and periderm. Dry mass (24 h at 75 °C) of each sample was determined and
14 expressed in mg per cm³ of soil. For more information about root sampling procedure see
15 Konopka et al. (submitted).

16 Oaks. In September 2003, nine sample trees of different stem diameter and representative of
17 the mean of their diameter classes were selected for harvest and destructive measurements to
18 estimate stand biomass. The trees were selected as follows: Firstly, trees were separated in
19 three groups of different DBH, and the mean DBH was calculated for each group. Finally, we
20 selected the individual tree whose DBH was closest to the mean of its group. The selected
21 trees were harvested and the crown separated from the main stem. Of each sample tree, stem
22 diameter was measured from the base to the top at 1 m intervals, as well as at breast height
23 (DBH). Also total tree height and depth of live crown were measured. Stem volume of the
24 sample trees was calculated by summing the volume of the one-meter sections, which were
25 calculated from their upper and lower diameter and assuming a truncated-cone shape. Stem
26 biomass was calculated by multiplying stem volume with stem density. Density of woody
27 samples was determined from the dry mass to fresh volume ratio. Stem density was
28 determined from discs sampled on each of the nine trees. From each tree, samples disks were
29 taken at one-fourth, one-third, half, and two-thirds of total height. Because no significant
30 differences in density were found among discs from individual trees, stem density of each tree
31 was calculated as the average density of the four discs sampled from each tree. Overall mean

1 stem density was then estimated as the mean of the densities of the nine trees and was 0.582
2 ton m⁻³.

3 Branch and leaf biomass of the sample trees was estimated as follows. All primary branches
4 from the nine trees were detached from the stems in the field, and diameter at the onset point
5 at the trunk of each single branch was then recorded. In three out of the nine felled trees, one
6 in the highest range of DBH, one in the average range and one in the lowest range, branch and
7 foliage biomass were studied in great detail. Of these three trees, total foliage biomass of every
8 single primary branch was collected carefully, oven-dried (24 h, 75 °C) and weighted. Branch
9 dry mass was calculated as follows. Fresh weight of each individual primary branch was
10 recorded and 30 branches, covering the whole range of branch diameter, were selected, oven-
11 dried (15 days, 70 °C) and finally weighted. The water percent contained at individual
12 branches was then calculated by means of a power function:

13

$$14 \quad \% \text{ Water} = 23.616 * D_o^{0.0757}$$

15

16 Where % Water is the percent of weight in water of the fresh branch, calculated as the ratio
17 of dry/fresh weight of each sampled branch, and D_o the diameter of the branch at the onset of
18 the trunk. Dry weight of each individual branch is the difference between the fresh weight and
19 the calculated amount of water. Allometric relationships were then developed between branch
20 diameter at the onset of the trunk and branch and foliage dry biomass (Table 2). Branch and
21 foliage biomass of the six remaining trees were then calculated using these allometric
22 relationships and the diameter recorded at each tree.

23

24 Stump biomass of the nine oak trees was determined by excavating and collecting the entire
25 stump. Stumps were then carefully washed and fresh biomass was determined. Coarse root (>
26 5mm) biomass was assessed following a similar approach as that used for branches. Diameter
27 at the base and the onset of every primary root in the stump were recorded for each tree.
28 Several primary roots, selected according to the diameter frequency distribution, were entirely
29 excavated and all root biomass down to 5 mm of diameter were collected. An allometric
30 function was then developed with the diameter of the root at the onset of the root (Table 2)

31

1 Allometric relationships were established between stem, branch, foliage, reproductive organs,
2 stumps and coarse root (> 5 mm) biomass (both age classes), and several tree characteristics:
3 DBH, tree height (H), crown length (CL), and $DBH^2 \cdot \text{height}$ (DBH^2H). Allometric
4 relationships with DBH only were consistently good (best R^2 and p-value). We decided
5 therefore to use the biomass – DBH relationships to estimate biomass at the stand level (Table
6 1). Stem, branch, foliage, stump and coarse root biomass were thus scaled-up to the stand
7 level by combining these allometric relationships with the DBH inventory of the entire stand.
8 Acorn biomass was collected in the three most intensively sampled trees, dried (2 days, 75
9 °C) and weighted. However, our observations suggest that the standing acorn biomass
10 could be seriously biased due to the biomass lost during tree felling. Therefore we used as
11 standing acorn biomass that acorn biomass collected in the litterfall.

12

13 Both biomass and necromass of fine and small roots were estimated in 2003 following
14 the same approach as explained above for pines.

15

16

1 *Net primary production*

2

3 Net primary production (NPP) during the period 2001-2003 was calculated by combining
4 changes in standing biomass, mean litterfall and fine root productivity during this period.

5 Productivity of standing woody biomass compartments (stem, branch and coarse root) was
6 determined as in Xiao et al. (2003):

7

8
$$\text{NPP}_{2001-2003} = (B_{2003} - B_{2001} + \text{BH}_{2001-2003})/3, \quad (1)$$

9

10 where $\text{NPP}_{2001-2003}$ is mean annual NPP for stem, branch and coarse root from 2001 to 2003,
11 B_{2001} is stem biomass during winter 2000-2001, B_{2003} is stem biomass during winter 2003-
12 2004, $\text{BH}_{2001-2003}$ is stem, branch and coarse necromass produced during the 3 years. This
13 necromass accounted for the branch litter collected in the litter traps and the tree mortality
14 due to the 2002 wind storm. Litterfall of stem bark was ignored because it was very small.
15 We determined the difference in standing woody biomass by combining the species-specific
16 allometric relationships described in Table 1 with the forests inventory data. Resulting
17 productivity values were then divided by three in order to obtain annual productivity.

18

19 NPP of foliage was calculated differently for each stand. In pine, NPP of needles was
20 estimated from the allometric relationship between current-year needles and DBH, and the
21 stand inventory data. Foliage NPP in oak was estimated directly from the foliage litterfall
22 during 2003. Productivity of reproductive organs was calculated by, assuming that
23 production equals litterfall. Litterfall was measured from 2001 to 2003 under the pine and
24 the oak canopy using respectively 10 and 19 randomly placed collectors (surface area of 0.3
25 m^2) with nylon-mesh netting. Thus the area sampling proportion to the plot area for litterfall
26 under the pine and the oak canopy is 0.015 % and 0.03%, respectively. All litter was oven-
27 dried (2 days, 75 °C) and sorted into branches, needles and reproductive organs. However,
28 litterfall of big branches (not collected by litter traps) was neglected. During spring and
29 beginning of summer of 2001 litter was not separated into the different fractions, and branch
30 and acorn litterfall were estimated by assuming the same proportion of leaf and acorn litter
31 to the total litter produced during 2003 and 2002.

1 Production, mortality and disappearance of fine roots (< 2 mm) and small roots (2 – 5 mm)
2 were estimated using the decision matrix of Fairley and Alexander (1985) and the
3 seasonal data on fine and small root biomass obtained during 2003 (Konopka et al.
4 submitted).. Several assumptions adopted in this decision matrix may have introduced
5 some degree of underestimation on fine root productivity. Because the matrix assumes
6 fine root decomposition to be 0 when necromass increases, it is likely that both mortality
7 and productivity have been underestimated. On the other hand productivity may have
8 also been overestimated because this study used all biomass increases, independently of
9 their statistical significance. The sum of the productivity between each sampling date was
10 then the annual productivity of fine roots and small roots at each stand.

11 Aboveground net primary production (ANPP) was determined as the sum of stem, branch,
12 needle (or leaf) and cone (or acorn) NPP. Belowground net primary production (BNPP) was
13 determined as the sum of coarse root (> 5 mm) NPP and fine root (< 5 mm) NPP.

14 *Forest C pools*

15
16
17 To study the total C store of both stands, the C stores in the organic surface layer and in the
18 mineral soil were determined in addition to the carbon in tree biomass. Fine root necromass
19 at the time of tree harvesting was included as belowground organic matter and not in the
20 mineral soil pool. The organic layer was a well defined mor-humus in the pines, composed of
21 a litter-, O_r - and an O_h -layer and with C contents superior to 30%. In the oaks, the surface
22 layer consisted of a moder-humus, with less-defined layers. The depth of this organic layer
23 averaged 4.4 cm in the pines and 5.6 cm in the oaks. The mineral soil assessed in this study
24 was limited to a depth of 30 cm. Hence, total soil C as well as total soil C sequestration were
25 probably underestimated here. However, we assumed that the largest differences in soil C
26 would appear in the surface layer and upper 30 cm of the mineral soil. Twenty-five 30 cm-
27 deep soil cores were taken from the mineral soil in August 2003 to estimate the soil carbon
28 concentration of each horizon in the organic and mineral soil. Roots were removed and soil
29 was dried and analyzed for C and N using dry combustion (NC 2100 Soil, CE Instruments,
30 Italy). Total C and N content in each horizon were calculated from the layer thickness, bulk
31 density and C concentration. Bulk density was measured in only five cores, and although

1 standard deviations were very low (around 7% of the bulk density), this adds uncertainty to
2 our estimates of soil C content. Biomass C pools were obtained from the standing biomass
3 and assuming a biomass C concentration of 50%.

4

5 *Soil pH measurements*

6 In the beginning of February 2002, 20 soil collars were removed, 10 in each of the two
7 stands. The collar content was divided in the organic layer and the mineral soil down to
8 approximately 10 cm in the mineral soil. The pH (CaCl₂) was determined for both the
9 organic layer and the mineral soil following the procedure of Schinner et al. (1995).

10

11 *Statistical analysis*

12 A non-linear least squares fitter (ORIGIN version 5.0; Northampton, MA USA) was used to
13 determine allometric relationships between biomass of stems, branches, needles and coarse
14 roots and DBH.

15

16

1 **Results**

3 *Forest inventory*

5 Scots pine stocking density in the pine stand in winter 2003-2004 was 362 trees ha⁻¹, a mean
6 tree height of 21.4 m (Xiao et al. 2003), mean DBH was 29.7 cm and median DBH was 29.1
7 cm. In winter 2000-2001 stocking density was 377 trees ha⁻¹ but during a severe storm in
8 November 2002, 15 trees fell. The negligible differences in the DBH frequency distribution
9 between winter 2000-2001 and 2003-2004 indicates that net diameter growth was very small
10 during the three years of this study (Figure 1a). Since 1984 this stand has been severely
11 thinned (last thinning in 1999 when 162.5 trees ha⁻¹ were harvested; Xiao et al. 2003). This
12 harvest explains the positive skewness in the DBH frequency distribution (Figure 1a).

13 Pedunculate oak stocking density in September 2003 was 310 trees ha⁻¹, mean tree height
14 17.2 m, mean DBH 25.9 cm, and median DBH was 24.0 cm. Figure 1b shows how the
15 diameter distribution has clearly shifted to the right, indicating a substantial increase in stem
16 diameter in this stand during the last three years. The frequency distribution of DBH classes
17 has the shape of a normal distribution (figure 1b). In contrast to the pine stand, the oak stand
18 has undergone only 2 thinnings during last 20 years, the last one 10 years ago.

20 *Scots pine*

22 *Standing Biomass*

23 Standing biomass per tree compartment based on the 2003-2004 winter inventory are shown
24 in Table 3. Total tree biomass in pine was 169.0 t ha⁻¹. Aboveground biomass totaled 143.9 t
25 ha⁻¹ and contained 85.1 % of total tree biomass (Figure 2a). Stem biomass and branch biomass
26 were 122.6 and 16.8 t ha⁻¹, and contained 72.5 % and 10.0 % of total biomass, respectively.
27 Needle biomass was 3.4 t ha⁻¹, comprising about 2 % of total biomass. About two-thirds of
28 total needle biomass was in current-year needles and one-third in one-year-old needles. Cone
29 biomass was estimated in 2003 as 1.1 t ha⁻¹, comprising 0.6 % of total biomass.
30 Total belowground biomass was 25.2 t ha⁻¹, and comprised about 15 % of total biomass (Table
31 3 and Figure 2a). Coarse root (> 5 mm) biomass amounted to 22.5 t ha⁻¹, i.e. about 13.2 % of

1 total biomass. Total fine root (< 5 mm) biomass in October 2003 was 2.7 t ha⁻¹, and
2 represented 1.6 % of total biomass (Table 3 and Figure 4). The biomass of live fine roots < 1
3 mm (1.4 t ha⁻¹) during the October 2003 campaign was significantly higher than that of the
4 other two diameter classes of live fine roots, *i.e.* 1-2 mm (0.5 t ha⁻¹) and 2-5 mm (0.8 t ha⁻¹).

5 6 *Net primary production*

7 Total NPP in the pine stand averaged over the 2001-2003 period was 8.1 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (Table 3).
8 More than half of total NPP was allocated to aboveground components (4.5 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, 56 %),
9 and a high proportion of it was invested in needles (2.2 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) and reproductive organs (1.5
10 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) production. Stem and branch production were surprisingly low (0.4 and 0.5 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹
11 ¹, respectively; Table 3) compared to their large contribution to total biomass (72.6 % and
12 10.0 % respectively). The relative proportions of total NPP of the different tree compartments
13 are shown in Figure 2b.

14 Total belowground NPP was 3.6 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, and comprised about 44.3 % of total NPP (Table 3
15 and Figure 2b). Coarse root NPP represented a relatively low proportion of total NPP (0.1 t
16 ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, 1.2 %). Fine root production was the most important contributor to total NPP (2.9 t
17 ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, equaling 43.1 % of total NPP). The NPP of fine roots of the different classes < 1 mm,
18 1-2 mm and 2-5 mm was 2.5, 0.4 and 0.6 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, respectively, and their relative proportions
19 in total NPP were 30.8 %, 4.7 % and 7.5 %, respectively (Table 3 and Figure 2b).

20 21 *Pedunculate oak*

22 23 *Standing biomass*

24 In winter 2003-2004, total tree biomass in the pedunculate oak stand was 176.5 t ha⁻¹ (Table
25 3). Aboveground biomass totaled 151.1 t ha⁻¹, therefore containing 85.6 % of total tree
26 biomass (Figure 2a). Stem biomass and branch biomass were 104.9 and 41.7 t ha⁻¹, containing
27 respectively 59.4 % and 23.6 % of total biomass. Foliage biomass in September 2003 was 4.3
28 t ha⁻¹, comprising about 2.4 % of total biomass. Acorn standing biomass was estimated in
29 2003 as 0.2 t ha⁻¹, comprising just the 0.1 % of the total phytomass.

30 Total belowground biomass was 25.4 t ha⁻¹, and comprised about 14.4 % of total biomass
31 (Table 3 and Figure 2). Coarse root (> 5 mm) biomass amounted to 21.7 t ha⁻¹, *i.e.* about 12

1 % of total biomass. Total fine root (< 5 mm) biomass measured in October 2003 was 3.8 t ha⁻¹
2 ¹, representing 2.1 % of total biomass (Table 3 and Figure 2). During the October 2003
3 campaign biomass of small roots (1.8 t ha⁻¹) was higher than the biomass of live fine roots (<
4 2 mm) (2.0 t ha⁻¹).

5 6 *Net primary production*

7 Total NPP in the oak stand averaged over the 2001-2003 period was 17.7 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (Table 3).
8 Unlike pine, oak allocated a large proportion of NPP to aboveground tree compartments (13.9
9 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, 78.5 % of total NPP). Most of the aboveground NPP was invested in woody biomass,
10 e. g. in stems (5.5 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) and in branches (3.5 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) (Figure 2b). Foliage production
11 accounted for 4.4 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (24.8 % of total NPP) and acorns production was rather low (0.6 t
12 ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, 3.3 % of total NPP).

13 Total belowground NPP was 3.7 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, and comprised about 21.0 % of total NPP (Table 3
14 and Figure 2b). Coarse root NPP represented approximately 6.2 % of total NPP (1.1 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹
15 ¹). Fine root represented 14.7 % total NPP (2.6 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹). The NPP of fine roots of the different
16 classes < 1 mm, 1-2 mm and 2-5 mm was 1.3, 0.5 and 0.8 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, respectively, and their
17 relative proportions in total NPP were 7.3 %, 2.8 % and 4.5 %, respectively (Table 3 and
18 Figure 2b).

19 20 *Soil carbon pools*

21 The total amount of C stored in soils amounted to 92.2 t C ha⁻¹ in the oak stand and 150.8
22 t C ha⁻¹ in the pine stand (Table 4). Total amount of C stored in the litter layer (O_l + O_f +
23 O_h) was slightly higher in pines than in oaks (33.9 t C ha⁻¹ and 26.5 t C ha⁻¹,
24 respectively). The largest differences were found in the mineral soil, where soil organic
25 matter in the pine was almost double than in oak (117 t C ha⁻¹ and 65.7 t C ha⁻¹,
26 respectively). In the oaks, soil organic matter was mainly concentrated in the litter layer
27 and the upper 5 cm of the mineral soil (more than 50 % of the total soil C was placed)
28 whereas soil organic matter in the pine stand was more distributed in the soil profile.

29 30 **Discussion**

31

1 *Standing biomass pine*

2 Total biomass in the pine stand (169 t dM ha⁻¹) was within the range for pine sp. reported in
3 a review by Vogt *et al.* (1991; Table 3). Aboveground biomass, however, was substantially
4 higher than the average aboveground phytomass of Belgian coniferous forests (96 t dM ha⁻¹
5 ¹; TBFRA-2000), which was mainly due to the relatively old age of this stand. Nonetheless,
6 aboveground biomass also exceeded the reported range of 11.3-134 t dM ha⁻¹ for pine sp.
7 (Vogt *et al.* 1991). Aboveground biomass also represented a very large proportion of total
8 biomass (85 % of total biomass), which was at the upper end of the range reported for Scots
9 pine stands (67.2-89.2 %; Vanninen *et al.* 1996; Gower *et al.* 1994) and for other pine species
10 (Knight *et al.* 1994).

11 Belowground woody biomass was thus relatively small and accounted for only 13% of total
12 biomass. This estimate of coarse root biomass is larger than the 10% estimated in Xiao *et al.*
13 (2003) for the same stand, which is due to the development and application of a new allometric
14 relationship that covers the entire range of root diameter classes. Geometric observations of
15 six other coarse root systems at this site (Cermák *et al.* 1998) also indicated relatively shallow
16 root systems, and thus probably also low coarse root biomass.

17 Fine root biomass was 2.7 t ha⁻¹, slightly lower than the 3.1 t ha⁻¹ observed in early March
18 2002 (Xiao *et al.* 2003). This difference was expected because in 2002 fine root biomass was
19 investigated down to 90 cm in the soil profile, whereas we only measured down to 30 cm in
20 the mineral soil. However, fine root biomass at this pine site is strongly concentrated in the
21 upper 30 cm of the soil profile (Janssens *et al.* 1999, Xiao *et al.* 2003). For instance, in the
22 Xiao *et al.* study (2003), 78, 60 and 65% of fine root biomass < 1mm, 1-2 mm and 2-5 mm,
23 respectively, were concentrated in these upper 30 cm. Applying the same ratios to this year's
24 fine root biomass in the upper 30 cm increases the total fine root biomass to 3.8 t ha⁻¹, 22%
25 higher as compared to 2001. This indicates that either interannual variability is very large, that
26 fine roots are still regrowing in response to the severe thinning that took place in 1999, or, as
27 will be discussed below, that there is a shift in C allocation to the belowground compartment.

28

29 *Standing biomass oak*

30 The estimated standing biomass in the oak plot was 176.5 t dM ha⁻¹, which was
31 considerably lower than the range of standing biomass reported by Schulze (1982) and

1 Vogt et al. (1991) for several temperate deciduous forests. However, these studies were
2 based on a limited number of deciduous stands. Furthermore, total aboveground biomass
3 at our site was significantly higher than the average aboveground phytomass in Belgian
4 deciduous forest estimated at 125 t ha⁻¹ (TBFRA-2000; probably an age related
5 phenomenon) but in the upper range of aboveground biomass reported by Vogt (1991)
6 (Table 3).

7
8 Although the stand was seven years younger than the pine stand and despite the fact that
9 the oak trees were shorter than the pine trees and tree density was smaller, total standing
10 phytomass in the oak stand was similar to that in the pine stand (176.5 versus 169.0 t ha⁻¹).
11 When comparing individual trees from the same DBH class, we observed much larger
12 biomass in oak than in pine trees (Figure 3). This was due to a combination of more
13 developed branch and coarse root systems and a higher wood density (0.582 versus 0.502
14 g cm⁻³). Stems were the largest biomass pool in the oak stand, accounting for more than
15 half of the live phytomass (57%; see Figure 2 and Table 3), followed by branches (23 %)
16 and coarse roots (14%). This pattern was also observed in another mixed oak-beech forest
17 in Belgium (Janssens et al. 1998). Scots pine, in contrast, allocated proportionally more
18 biomass to stems (72.5 %) at the expense especially of branches, which in pine only
19 accounted for 13 % of the total biomass.

20
21 Despite the different biomass distribution among aboveground compartments, the ratio of
22 above/belowground biomass was very similar in both species (Figure 2a, Table 3).

23 Therefore, habitat-specific variables were likely more important controlling factors of
24 biomass distribution patterns than species-specific ontogenetic development. In this
25 particular forest, roots may not need to penetrate deep in the soil because the clay layer
26 prevents the soil from drying out and gives structural support (Janssens et al. 1999). On the
27 other hand, it is likely that competition for light has been very important during the first
28 50 years of development, because tree density at both stands was kept above 1000 trees
29 ha⁻¹ until 1984 (Mark Schuermans, personal communication). Thus, it is likely that the
30 current high ratio of aboveground/belowground biomass is the legacy of past
31 management, or the lack of.

1

2 The proportion of standing biomass in fine roots and foliage was, as expected for an
3 almost 70-year-old forest, low (2.88 and 2.37 respectively), while the proportion
4 reproductive organs (acorns) biomass was negligible. However, fine root biomass
5 measurements in spring 2001 (Grassi, 2001) suggested that only 50 % of the total fine root
6 biomass in this oak stand was located in the upper 30 cm of the soil profile. Therefore, the
7 total fine root biomass in the oaks was probably twice as high as the 2.9 t ha⁻¹ reported here.

8

9 *NPP pine*

10 The NPP value of 8.1 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ in the pine stand was below the range of productivity for
11 coniferous stands reported by Vogt et al. (1991) and Schulze et al. (1982) (Table 3).
12 Productivity values for the same stand were 12.3 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ for the period 1995-1999 (before
13 the last thinning) and 8.5 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ in 2000 after the last thinning (Xiao et al. 2003). Thus,
14 NPP has not recovered since the last thinning. Cousens (1974) showed that Scots pine
15 productivity declines sharply after the age of 50 years and our productivity values agreed
16 remarkably well with that reported in this study for 75-years-old Scots pine stands in the
17 UK. It is therefore likely that the observed decline in productivity might be due to the aging
18 of the stand. Several mechanisms have been reported to be responsible of age-related
19 productivity decline, but among them the most claimed are: 1) Increases in maintenance
20 respiration of woody tissues; 2) nutrient limitation due to woody debris accumulation; and
21 3) Hydraulic limitation due to increases in resistance (Ryan and Yoder 1997). However
22 because this stand has been heavily managed, it would be difficult to distinguish the aging
23 effect from that induced by stand management.

24

25 During the period of this study, only 57% of the NPP was allocated to aboveground
26 compartments, 13% less than during the period 2000-2001 (Xiao et al. 2003). Thus, there
27 was a shift in the allocation of NPP to the belowground components in recent years. As a
28 result of this substantial shift to the belowground tissues, pine roots (< 5 mm) contributed
29 most to total NPP (43.1 %). Enhanced allocation of NPP to fine roots has been attributed
30 to nutrient limitations (Grier et al. 1981, Gholz et al. 1982). Recent observations at this
31 study site have indeed shown that, likely due to acidification of the soil, there have been

1 substantial losses of base cations, especially Ca, Mg and K (Neiryneck et al. 2002). Also
2 the intensive thinnings during the 1990's will have removed considerable amounts of
3 base cations from the site. Compared with estimates in 1992, pH has decreased by 20 %
4 (from 3.3 to 2.64) in the organic layer (Figure 6) and by 7% in the upper mineral soil
5 (from 3.0 to 2.78). This decrease in pH may also have affected the availability of
6 phosphorus because it precipitates as Al- and Fe-phosphates under acid conditions. We
7 therefore hypothesize that the ongoing nutrient losses in this already nutrient poor soil
8 have reduced nutrient availability and thus plant productivity. There are also indications
9 that heterotrophic activity is limited in this acid, nutrient poor soil. Firstly, C inputs via
10 above- and belowground litterfall amounted to 4.0 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Adding the input of slash
11 remaining after the 1999 thinning (divided by the number of years since the thinning)
12 brings the total C inputs to the soil to 7.5 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Total soil respiration was 4.2 t C
13 ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Curiel Yuste et al. submitted). Assuming that 50% of soil respiration originates
14 from decomposition processes (Trumbore et al., 1995, Hanson 2000, Hogberg et al.
15 2001), heterotrophs decomposed only 2.1 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Thus, less than one third of the
16 organic matter inputs to the soil were mineralized by the heterotrophs and 72 % of the
17 inputs (approximately 5.4 t C ha⁻¹) remained unprocessed in the soil. Indeed, the large
18 accumulation of organic matter observed when comparing our soil C data (Table 4) with
19 that from 1996 (Janssens et al. 1999) support this observation. According to these
20 estimates C has been accumulated in pine soil at an average rate of 6.6 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which
21 agreed well with the estimates above. It is therefore also likely that heterotrophic activity
22 is seriously limited in this acid, nutrient-poor pine stand. Because microbes are
23 responsible for nutrient mineralization and subsequent nutrient availability for root
24 uptake, the nutrient recycling capacity is limited, creating a negative feedback that may
25 influence plant productivity. Although the relationship between biogeochemistry and
26 community productivity are complex and still not well understood (Lockaby 1995),
27 decomposition rates may control productivity by enhancing positive feedbacks on soil
28 nutrient availability (Pastor et al. 1984, Gower and Son 1992). The low values of
29 productivity observed at our pine site may therefore be related to the low mineralization
30 rates observed at this stand.

31

1 *NPP oak*

2 Despite the differences in tree density (310 tree ha⁻¹ and 361 tree ha⁻¹ in oak and pine,
3 respectively) and the similarity in habitats and age of both stands, NPP during the period
4 2001 –2003 was twice as high in the oak stand as in the neighboring pine stand (Table 3).
5 Figure 4 shows that with the exception of the reproductive organs and fine roots, NPP of
6 all other tissues was higher in the oak than in the pine stand. Unlike pine, oaks did not
7 seem to be affected by severe nutrient limitation. Net primary production over the period
8 2001-2003 was in the middle of the range reported by Vogt (1991) and above the range
9 reported by Schulze (1982) for several deciduous temperate forests (Table 3). Moreover,
10 our aboveground NPP value (ANPP) was in the middle range of a normal distribution of
11 ANPP of deciduous forest in the temperate area (Reich and Bolstad 2001).

12
13 In contrast with pine, oak clearly invested most of NPP in aboveground compartments
14 (more than 78 % of total NPP, Figure 2b), indicating that nutrient stress was probably
15 limited. A large proportion of NPP was allocated to woody production (57 % of total
16 NPP), especially to stems (30 % of total NPP). Because woody tissues have a lesser
17 priority for assimilates than fine roots and foliage (Cannell 1985), the large allocation of
18 NPP to wood suggests that oaks were growing under optimal conditions.
19 Moreover, also the heterotrophic activity in the oak stand did not seem to be as limited as
20 in the pine stand. The input of above- and belowground litter was 4 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, and total
21 soil respiration was 8.5 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Curiel Yuste et al. submitted). Assuming again that
22 50% of soil respiration originates from decomposition processes, 4.2 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ would
23 be mineralized, roughly equal to the C inputs. Thus, soil heterotrophs in the oaks did not
24 seem to be affected by nutrient limitation or the acid conditions, as appeared to be the
25 case under pine.

26
27 It is surprising that, although both stands grow under the same climatic and edaphic
28 conditions, the oak stand did not suffer the same limitations to productivity and
29 heterotrophic activity as the pines. Two observations may help to understand the
30 differences found between sites. Firstly, in comparison to the oaks, pines stored a larger
31 amount of C in the organic and mineral soil than oaks (Figure 5, Table 4). According to

1 the similarity in the litter inputs over the last three years (table 3), these differences in soil
2 C suggests that the heterotrophs in pine processed the plant detritus more slowly. The
3 residence time of C in the organic layer, calculated as the ratio of the amount of C from
4 litter over the total C in the soil, was almost 40% shorter in oaks than in pines (23 versus
5 38 years). We therefore hypothesize that the large soil organic matter pool and its long
6 residence time in the pine stand was the result of the refractory nature of the pine litter.
7 This slow mineralization probably resulted in the immobilization of large amounts of
8 nutrients in non-processed organic matter, and hence reduced nutrient availability for
9 plant growth. It is well known that deciduous litter normally decomposes faster than
10 coniferous litter (Lockaby et al. 1995, Hobbie et al. 2000, Kavvadias et al. 2001). In
11 general, litter from evergreen species tend to have both higher lignin and lower nutrient
12 concentrations than litter from deciduous species (Coley et al. 1985) and decomposition
13 is generally slower for litter with high lignin concentration and low nutrient
14 concentrations (Van Cleve 1974, Heal et al. 1981, Hobbie 1996). Therefore, the
15 refractory nature of the coniferous may have retarded nutrient cycling rates and its
16 availability for plant growth. Unfortunately, detailed chemical characterization of the soil
17 in the oak stand was not available.

18
19 Secondly, we did observe a higher pH in the organic layer of the oak stand (Figure 6).
20 Although both soils were very acid, the pH of the organic soil layer in the pine stand was
21 below 3.0. The consequences of this little difference in pH might be relevant for two
22 reasons. First because in very acid soils slight changes in pH lead to large changes in
23 soluble Al^{3+} (Smith and Hem 1972) which is directly responsible of a large range of
24 physiological and biochemical changes in plant and microbes (Wild 1988). Large
25 amounts of this cation have been reported to affect the permeability of the root
26 membranes for ions and water, but also cell division, respiration, Nitrogen metabolism or
27 phosphorylation of glucose (Clarkson 1969). Second because these pH values were close
28 to the threshold of the aluminum- and iron buffer regions. At pH values below 3.0, as
29 were found in the organic layer of the pine stand, not only Al^{3+} but also Fe^{3+} is liberated
30 by dissociation of Al- Fe-organic matter complexes. These acidic cations replace base
31 cations such as Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} at the exchange sites, which subsequently are leached and

1 lost. We therefore hypothesize that in contrast to oak, the more acid pine litter has
2 contributed to the acceleration of the acidification process, and hence, of nutrient losses
3 in these already nutrient poor, acid soils. Pine litter is rich in refractory polyphenolics,
4 which decompose slowly and promote the generation and release of humic and fulvic
5 acids (Schnitzer & Kahn 1979). This release of organic acids is directly responsible for
6 soil acidification, promoting the loss of base cations. High sand contents also enhance the
7 mobility of organic acids and thus facilitate the leaching of nutrients (Fenwick and Knapp
8 1982). Moreover, it is also likely that the base cation pool from the pine stand has been
9 depleted at a faster rate because of the removal of phytomass during the recent intensive
10 thinnings.

11
12 Figure 7 schematizes the most important differences in nutrient cycling between the oak
13 and pine stand, and its effects on plant growth. In the pines, soil organic matter
14 mineralization (R_h) appeared to exert the key control, and was limited by the poor quality
15 of the plant detritus, the extreme acidity (pH) of the soil, and perhaps the poor nutrient
16 availability in the soil. In the oak stand, in contrast, pH was low but not as low, thus
17 probably limited heterotrophic activity to a lesser degree. Oak litter is also more palatable
18 and less acidifying than pine litter, and clearly nutrient mineralization rates did not limit
19 tree growth in the oak stand.

21 **Conclusions**

22 Despite the fact that both species were growing under the same environmental and
23 topographic conditions, Scots pine and pedunculate oak showed very different
24 productivity rates and C allocation patterns. The NPP in the oak stand was much higher
25 than in the pine stand. Despite the lower NPP the soil C pool was much larger in the
26 pines than in the oak stand. Our results suggest that, in this nutrient-poor soil, plant
27 productivity largely depended on the capacity of heterotrophs to mineralize the organic
28 matter inputs and recycle nutrients, and that heterotrophic activity depended on the
29 amount and chemical characteristics of the plant detritus. In the acid, low buffer capacity
30 conditions of these sandy soils, the deciduous species was more productive than the
31 coniferous strategy. The acidifying and refractory nature of pine litter accelerated soil

1 acidification, depleted the soil base cation pool and immobilized another part of it.
2 Although oak soil was also in a very developed state of acidification, the more easily
3 decomposable, less acid litter input may probably stimulate the mineralization of organic
4 matter providing a continuous source of nutrients to plant growth and heterotrophic
5 activity.

6

7 **Acknowledgments**

8 *This study was in part financially supported by the Fifth Framework Programme of the*
9 *European Commission (R&TD programme) through the CARBOEUROFLUX (contract*
10 *EVK2-CT-1999-00032) and the MEFYQUE (QLKS-CT-2001-00345) research contracts.*
11 *This study contributes to the Global Change and Terrestrial Ecosystems (GCTE) Core*
12 *Project of the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP). The authors*
13 *gratefully acknowledge the field work collaboration of Jana De Clerck, Melina Kyametis*
14 *and Gabriele Guidolotti. The authors also thank F. Kockelbergh and Nadine Calluy for*
15 *technical assistance, the Institute for Forestry and Game Management for logistic support*
16 *at the stand and forest ranger Marc Schuermans for his help and advice. JCY wants to*
17 *thank Sarah Bracke for her disinterested help and support.*

18

1 Bibliography

- 2
- 3 Baeyens, L., J. Van Slycken, and D. Stevens. 1993. Description of the soil profile in Brasschaat. Internal
4 research paper, Institute for Forestry and Game Management, Geraardsbergen, Belgium, 17 pp.
- 5 Cannell, M. G. R. 1985. Dry matter partitioning in tree crops. *In* Trees as crop plants. Eds. M. G. R.
6 Cannell and J. E. Jackson. NERC, Huntingdon, pp 160-193.
- 7 Cermák, J., F. Riguzzi, and R. Ceulemans. 1998. Scaling up from the individual tree to the stand level in
8 Scots pine. I. Needle distribution, overall crown and root geometry. *Annales des Sciences*
9 *Forestières*. 55: 63-88.
- 10 Ciais, P., P. P. Tans, M. Trolier, J. W. C. White, and R. J. Francey. 1995. A large northern hemisphere
11 terrestrial CO₂ sink indicated by the ¹³C/¹²C ration of atmospheric CO₂. *Science*. 269: 1098-
12 1101.
- 13 Clarkson D.T., 1969. Metabolic aspects of aluminum toxicity and some possible mechanisms for
14 resistance. *In* Ecological Aspects of the Mineral Nutrition of Plants. Ed. Rorison H. Blackwell
15 Scientific Public, UK, pp. 381–397,
- 16 Cousens, J. 1974. An introduction to woodland ecology. Oliver and Boyd, Edinburg, UK.
- 17 Cramer, W., J. R. J. Olson, S.T. Prince, J. M. O. Scurlock, and Members of the GPPDI. 2001. Determining
18 present patterns of global productivity. *In* Terrestrial Global Productivity. Eds. J. Roy, B. Saugier,
19 and H. A. Mooney. Academic Press, San Diego, pp 429-448.
- 20 Curiel Yuste, J., I. A. Janssens, A. Carrara, and R. Ceulemans. 2004. Annual Q₁₀ of soil respiration reflects
21 plant phenological patterns as well as temperature sensitivity. *Global Change Biology*. 10: 161-
22 169.
- 23 Curiel Yuste, J., I. A. Janssens, A. Carrara, L. Meiresonne, and R. Ceulemans. 2003. Interactive effect of
24 temperature and precipitation on soil respiration in a temperate maritime pine forest. *Tree*
25 *Physiology*. 23: 1263-1270.
- 26 De Pury, D. G. G. and G. D. Farquhar. 1997. Simple scaling of photosynthesis from leaves to canopies
27 without the errors of big-leaf models. *Plant, Cell and Environment*. 20: 537-557.
- 28 Dobris Assessment. 1995. Nature and Wildlife. *In* Europe's Environment. Eds. D. Stanners and P.
29 Bourdeau. European Environmental Agency, Copenhagen, pp. 193
- 30 Fairley R. I. and I. J. Alexander. 1985. Methods of calculating fine root production in forests. *In* Ecological
31 Interactions in Soil. Ed. A H Fitter. Special Publication of the British Ecological Society, Vol.
32 4, pp. 37-42.
- 33 Fenwick, J. M. and B. J. Knapp. 1982. Soils. Process and Response. London. Duckworth.
- 34 Gholz, H. L. and R. F. Fisher. 1982. Organic matter production and distribution in slash pine (*Pinus elliotii*)
35 plantations. *Ecology*. 63: 1827-1839.
- 36 Gholz, H. L.. 1982. Environmental limits on aboveground net primary production, leaf area and biomass in
37 vegetation zones of the Pacific Northwest. *Ecology*. 53: 469-481.

- 1 Gower S. T. and Y. Son. 1992. Differences in soil and leaf litterfall nitrogen dynamics for five forest
2 plantations. *Soil Scientific of America Journal*. 56: 1059-1066.
- 3 Gower, S.T., H.L. Gholz, K. Nakane and V.C. Baldwin. 1994. Production and carbon allocation patterns of pine
4 forests. *Ecology Bulletins*. 43:115-135.
- 5 Grier, C. C., K. A. Vogt, M. R. Keyes, and R. L. Edmonds. 1981. Biomass distribution and above- and
6 belowground production in young and mature *Abies amabilis* zone ecosystems of the Washington
7 Cascades. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*. 11: 155-167.
- 8 Hanson, P. J., N. T. Edwards, C. T. Garten, and J. A. Andrews. 2000. Separating root and microbial
9 contributions to soil respiration: A review of methods and observations. *Biogeochemistry*. 48:
10 115-146.
- 11 Heal O. W., P. W. Flanagan, D. D. French, S. F. Jr. Maclean. 1981. Decomposition and accumulation of
12 organic matter in tundra. *In Tundra Ecosystems: a Comparative Analysis*. Eds Bliss LC et al.
13 Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, pp 587-633.
- 14 Hobbie, S. E. 1996. Temperature and plant species control over litter decomposition in Alaskan tundra.
15 *Ecological Monographs*. 66(4): 503-522.
- 16 Hobbie, S. E., J. P. Schimel, S. E. Trumbore, and J. R. Randerson. 2000. Controls over carbon storage and
17 turnover in high-latitude soils. *Global Change Biology*. 6(Suppl. 1): 196-210.
- 18 Hogberg, P., A. Nordgren, N. Buchmann, A. F. S. Taylor, A. Akblad, M. N. Hogberg, G. Nyberg, M.
19 Ottosson-Lofvenius, and D. J. Read. 2001. Large-scale forest girdling shows that current
20 photosynthesis drives soil respiration. *Nature*. 411(14 juni): 789-792.
- 21 IPCC, (2001), "Third Assessment Report - Climate Change 2001". the third assessment report of the
22 intergovernmental panel on climate change, IPCC/WMO/UNEP.
- 23 Janssens, I. A., H. Lankreijer, G. Matteucci, A. S. Kowalski, N. Buchmann, D. Epron, K. Pilegaard, W.
24 Kutsch, B. Longdoz, T. Grünwald, L. Montagnani, S. Dore, C. Rebmann, E. J. Moors, A. Grelle,
25 Ü. Rannik, K. Morgenstern, R. Clement, S. Oltchev, J. Guðmundsson, S. Minerbi, P. Berbigier, A.
26 Ibrom, J. Moncrieff, M. Aubinet, C. Bernhofer, N. O. Jensen, T. Vesala, A. Granier, E.-D.
27 Schulze, A. Lindroth, A. J. Dolman, P. G. Jarvis, R. Ceulemans, and R. Valentini. 2001.
28 Productivity overshadows temperature in determining soil and ecosystem respiration across
29 European forests. *Global Change Biology*. 7: 269-278.
- 30 Janssens, I. A., L. Meiresonne, and R. Ceulemans. 2000. Mean soil CO₂ efflux from a mixed forest :
31 temporal and spatial integration. *Forest Ecosystem Modelling, Upscaling and Remote Sensing*, R.
32 Ceulemans, F. Veroustraete, V. Gond, and J. Van Rensbergen, eds., SPB Academic Publishing,
33 The Hague, 19-33.
- 34 Janssens, I. A., D. A. Sampson, J. Cermak, L. Meiresonne, F. Riguzzi, S. Overloop, and R. Ceulemans.
35 1999. Above- and below-ground phytomass and carbon storage in a Belgian Scots pine stand.
36 *Annals of Forest Science*. 56: 81-90.

- 1 Janssens, I. A., M. Schauvliege, R. Samson, N. Lust, and R. Ceulemans. 1998. Studie van de koolstofbalans
2 van -, en de koolstofopslag in het Vlaamse bos. .
- 3 Kavadias, V. A., D. Alifragis, A. Tsiontsis, G. Brofas, and G. Stamatelos. 2001. Litterfal, litter
4 accumulation and litter decomposition rates in four forest ecosystems in northern Greece. *Forest
5 Ecology and Management*. 144: 113-127.
- 6 Knight, D.H., J. Vose, V.C. Baldwin and K.C. Ewel. 1994. Contrasting patterns in pine forest ecosystems.
7 *Ecology Bulletins* 43:9-19.
- 8 Kowalski, A. S., S. Overloop, and R. Ceulemans. 2000. Eddy fluxes above a Belgian, Campine forest and
9 their relationship with predicting variables. *Forest Ecosystem Modelling, Upscaling and Remote
10 Sensing*, R. Ceulemans, F. Veroustraete, V. Gond, and J. Van Rensbergen, eds., SPB Academic
11 Publishing, The Hague, 3-17.
- 12 Lockaby, B. G., J. H. Miller, and R. G. Clawson. 1995. Influences of community composition on
13 biogeochemistry of Loblolly pine (*Pinus Taeda*) systems. *American Midland Naturalist*. 134: 176-
14 184.
- 15 Neiryneck, J., E. Van Ranst, P. Roskams, and N. Lust. 2002. Impact of decreasing throughfall depositions
16 on soil solution chemistry at coniferous monitoring sites in northern Belgium. *Forest Ecology and
17 Management*. 160: 127-142.
- 18 Oleksyn, J., R. Zytowiak, P. Karolewski, P. B. Reich, and M. G. Tjoelker. 2000. Genetic and
19 environmental control of seasonal carbohydrate dynamics in trees of diverse *Pinus sylvestris*
20 populations. *Tree Physiology*. 20: 837-847.
- 21 Pastor, J., J. D. Aber, C. A. McLaugherty and J. M. Melillo. 1984. Aboveground production and N and P
22 cycling along a nitrogen mineralization gradient on Blackhawk Island, Wisconsin. *Ecology* 65:
23 256-268.
- 24 Reich, P. B., and P. Bolstad. 2001. Productivity of evergreen and deciduous temperate forest. *In Terrestrial
25 Global Productivity*. Eds. J. Roy, B. Saugier, and H. A. Mooney. Academic Press, San Diego, pp
26 245-277.
- 27 Reich, P. B., D. F. Grigal, J. D. Aber, and S. T. Gower. 1997. Nitrogen mineralization and productivity in
28 50 hardwood and conifer stands on diverse soils. *Ecology*. 78: 335-347.
- 29 Running, S. W. 1994. Testing forest-BGC ecosystem process simulations across a climatic gradient in
30 Oregon. *Ecological Applications*. 4: 238-247.
- 31 Ryan, M. G., and B. J. Yoder. 1997. Hydraulic limits tree height and tree growth. *BioScience*. 47(4): 235-
32 242.
- 33 Schnitzer, M. and Kahn, S. U. 1979. *Soil Organic Matter*. New York, Elsevier.
- 34 Schinner, F., R. Öhlinger, E. Kandeler, and R. Margesin. 1995. *Methods in Soil Biology*, Springer-Verlag,
35 Berlin.

- 1 Schulze, D. 1982. Plant life forms and their carbon, water and nutrient relations. *Physiological Plant*
2 Ecology II., O. L. Lange, P. S. Nobel, C. B. Osmond, and H. Ziegler, eds., Springer-Verlag,
3 Berlin, 615-676.
- 4 Smith, R.W. and J.D. Hem. 1972. Effect of aging on aluminum hydroxide complexes in dilute aqueous
5 solutions. U.S. Geological Survey Water-Supply Paper 1827-D.
- 6 Stenberg, P., T. Kuuluvainen, S. Kellomäki, J. C. Grace, E. J. Jokela, and H. L. Gholz. 1994. Crown
7 structure, light interception and productivity of pine trees and stands. *Ecological Bulletins*. 43: 20-
8 34.
- 9 TBFRA:UN-ECE/FAO. 2000. Forest Resources of Europe, CIS, North America, Australia, Japan and New
10 Zealand. Timber and Forest Study Papers No. 17, UN-ECE, Geneva.
- 11 Trumbore, S. E., E. A. Davidson, P. Barbosa de Camargo, D. C. Nepstad, and L. A. Martinelli. 1995.
12 Belowground cycling of carbon in forests and pastures of Eastern Amazonia. *Global*
13 *Biogeochemical Cycles*. 9(4): 515-528.
- 14 Van Cleve K. 1974. Organic matter quality in relation to decomposition. *In Soil Organism and*
15 *Decomposition in Tundra*. Eds. Holding A.J. et al. Tundra Biome Steering Committee, Stockholm,
16 pp 311-324.
- 17 Vanninen, P., H. Ylitalo, R. Sievänen and A. Mäkelä. 1996. Effects of age and site quality on the distribution of
18 biomass in Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.). *Trees-Structure & Function* 10:231-238.
- 19 Vogt, K. A. 1991. Carbon budgets of temperate forest ecosystems. *Tree Physiology*. 9: 69-86.
- 20 Wild, A. 1988. Russell's soil conditions and plant growth. Eds. Wild, A. Longman Group UK Limited,
21 London, p 909.
- 22 Xiao, C.-W., J. Curiel Yuste, I. A. Janssens, P. Roskams, L. Nachtergale, A. Carrara, B. Y. Sanchez, and R.
23 Ceulemans. 2003. Above- and belowground biomass and net primary production in a 73-year-old
24 Scots pine forest. *Tree Physiology*. 23: 505-516.
- 25
- 26

1 **Figure captions**

2

3 **Figure 1.** Frequency distribution of diameter at breast height (DBH) in the pine and oak
4 stands based on the inventories performed during the winter 2000 –2001 (2001) and the
5 winter 2003 – 2004 (2003).

6 **Figure 2.** Relative distribution of standing biomass at each tree compartment (a) and
7 proportion of net primary production (NPP) allocated to the different tree compartments
8 (b) in the oak and the pine stands, respectively.

9 **Figure 3.** Comparison of total biomass at each woody compartment (branches, stem and
10 coarse roots) of individual pines and oak trees from different diameters classes (DBH 24,
11 2, 32 and 40 cm).

12 **Figure 4.** Absolute differences in net primary production (NPP) allocation to the
13 different tree compartments in the oak and the pine stand ($\text{t dM ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). Positive values
14 mean that the absolute value of NPP for a given tree compartment was higher in oak than
15 in pine. Negative values mean that the NPP value was higher in pine.

16 **Figure 5.** Relative proportion of the tree major carbon (C) pools (Phytomass, organic soil
17 and mineral soil) in the oak and the pine stands, respectively.

18 **Figure 6.** pH values (CaCl_2) of the organic soil layer ($\text{O}_r + \text{O}_h$) in the pine stand for the
19 years 1992 and 2002. Labels in the right side of the graph represent the different buffer
20 regions of soil. Vertical bars represent the threshold the buffer regions of soil.

21 **Figure 7.** Schematic representation of the most important pathways in nutrient and
22 carbon forest fluxes in the oak (Oaks) and the pine (Pines) stands. Forest compartments
23 (phytomass, soil organic matter, microbes and nutrients available) are represented as
24 boxes. Solid lines represent fluxes of nutrients or organic matter and dotted lines
25 represent controls affecting the forest compartments. Soil organic matter (SOM), Litter
26 quality control (LQC), soil organic matter (SOM), Carbon in soil organic matter (SOM-
27 C), Nutrients in soil organic matter (SOM-Nt), above- and belowground net primary
28 production (ANPP and BNPP, respectively), above- and belowground biomass (AG and
29 BG biomass, respectively), heterotrophic respiration (C-efflux) and net change at each
30 pool (Δ).Numbers represent inputs and outputs (litter and C-flux) as well as pools. The

1 net limiting effect of a flux or a control over each of the forest compartments is
2 represented as (0) (no limitation) and (-) (negative limitation).

3

4 **Figure 1**

5

6

7

8

1 **Figure 2**

2

3

4

1 **Figure 3**

2

3

4

1 **Figure 4**

2

3

4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Table 1. Allometric relationships between tree component biomass and diameter at breast height (DBH) in the oak and the pine stand, respectively. Coefficients a and b for the power ($y = a * DBH^b$) and the exponential ($y = a * e^{b * DBH}$) functions are shown. Correlation coefficient (R^2) and p-value are also shown.

Component	Equation	Oaks				Pines				
		Coefficient		Statistics		Coefficient		Statistics		
		a	b	R^2	p-value	a	b	R^2	p-value	
Stem biomass	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0654	2.5753	0.9937	<0.00001	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.1227	2.3272	0.9988	<0.001
Branch biomass	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0021	3.3064	0.942	<0.00001	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0022	2.9123	0.9461	<0.001
Foliage biomass	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0024	2.6081	0.9102	<0.00001	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0045	2.2372	0.9267	<0.001
Stump biomass	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0103	2.5443	0.9583	<0.00001	$y = a * DBH^b$				
Coarse root biomass	$y = a * e^{b * DBH}$	1.8984	0.0856	0.9594	<0.00001	$y = a * DBH^b$	0.0035	2.8618	0.96	<0.005

Table 2. Allometric relationship in the oak stand between diameter of branch at the onset of the trunk (D_b), branch biomass (B_b) and foliage biomass (F_b) and diameter coarse root at the onset of the stump (D_r) and coarse root biomass (R_b). Correlation coefficient (R^2) and p-value are also shown.

Component	Equation	Coefficients				Statistics	
		a	b	c	d	R^2	p-value
Branch biomass	$B_b = a * (D_b - b) * (D_b - c) * (D_b - (b + c) / 2) + d$	0.000017	0.3	2.5	0.3	0.987	<0.00001
Coarse root biomass	$R_b = a * (D_r - b) * (D_r - c) * (D_r - (b + c) / 2) + d$	2.93E-07	107.06	-355.8	1.46	0.986	<0.00001
Foliage biomass	$F_b = a * D_b^b$	0.00009	2.1094			0.72	<0.00001

Table 3. Biomass distribution in tons of dry matter per year (ton dM ha⁻¹) at each tree compartment and net primary production (NPP) allocation to the different tree compartments in the oak and the pine stand. Ranges of Biomass and NPP from Vogt et al. (1991) and Schulze (1982) are also shown. Asterisks mean that the value corresponded to a single study.

Component	ton dM ha ⁻¹			ton dM ha ⁻¹		
	Pedunculate oak	Broadleaf (Vogt 1991)	Deciduous (Schulze 1982)	Scots pine	Pinus sp. (Vogt 1991)	Coniferous (Schulze 1982)
Stem biomass	104.9			122.6		
Branch biomass	41.7			16.8		
Foliage biomass	4.3	2.9 - 9.7		3.4	1.5 - 5.9	
Acorns/cones biomass	0.2			1.1		
Above total biomass	151.1	133.2 - 345.2	115 - 585.5	143.9	11.3 - 134	
Coarse roots (> 5 mm) biomass	21.7			22.5		
Small roots (2-5 mm) biomass	1.8			0.8		
Fine roots (<2 mm) biomass	2	2.5 - 8.5		1.9	0.26 - 22.4	
Below total biomass	25.4	36.0 *		25.2	14 - 40.3	
Forest total biomass	176.5	564.9 *	186 - 369	169	25.3 - 245.9	316 - 732
Stem NPP	5.5			0.4		
Branch NPP	3.5			0.5		
Foliage NPP	4.4	2.6 - 5.4		2.2	1.1 - 5.32	
Acorns/cones NPP	0.6			1.5		
Above total NPP	13.9	5.8 - 11.4		4.5	4.5 - 29.8	
Coarse roots (> 5 mm) NPP	1.1			0.1		
Small roots (2-5 mm) NPP	0.8			0.6		
Fine roots (<2 mm) NPP	1.8	2.4 - 6.6		2.9	0.4 - 4.2	
Below total NPP	3.7	5.0 - 8.8		3.6	4.9 - 11.32	
Forest total NPP	17.7	10 - 30.8	10 - 15	8.1	8.52 - 48	9 - 25
Foliage litter	4.4			2.7		
Branch litter	0.8			0.4		
Reproductive organs litter	0.6			1.5		

Total aboveground litter	5.8	4.6
--------------------------	-----	-----

Table 4. Bulk density, carbon concentration (%C) and total C in different layers of the soil profile of both, the oak and the pine stand, respectively.

Depth	Oaks			Pines		
	bulk density (g/cm ³)	% C	Total C (T/ha)	bulk density (g/cm ³)	% C	Total C (T/ha)
Litter layer		44.5	26.5		44.1	33.9
0-5 cm	1.1	3.8	21.5	1.2	5.0	30.1
5-10 cm	1.2	1.3	7.4	1.4	1.9	25.9
10-15 cm	1.1	1.0	7.2	1.4	1.7	22.8
15-30 cm	1.2	0.8	12.9	1.4	1.5	20.8
30-50 cm	1.3	0.6	16.7	1.5	0.8	17.4
Mineral soil			65.7			117.0
Total			92.2			150.8